

Study to Assess the Knowledge on Behavioral Problems of School Children among School Teachers with a View to Develop an Informational Module in Selected Schools at Chhattarpur, Madhya Pradesh

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study to assess the knowledge on behavioral problems of school children among school teachers. Descriptive research design was adopted for this study. The population for the study includes school teachers who are handling the students in the age group between 6-12 years. The sample selected for the present study was 60 school teachers who fulfilled the inclusion criteria. Purposive sampling technique was adopted for the study. The study result shows that the knowledge of school teachers on behavioral problems of school children shows that 15 [25%] of school teachers having moderately adequate knowledge and 45[75%] of them have inadequate knowledge and none of the school teachers had adequate knowledge regarding behavioral problems of school children among school teachers. The mean and standard deviation of the study is 14.02 +4.26. The study concluded that knowledge of school teachers regarding behavioral problem were poor, so there is a need to improve the knowledge of school teachers about behavioral problem of school children.

Keywords: Behavioral problems, school children, school teachers

INTRODUCTION

School age is the period between 6-12 years. Scholars are emerging as creative persons who are preparing for their future role in society. The school years are a time of new achievement and new experiences. Children's individual needs and preferences should be respected. A child, who is productive and engaged in the school experience, whether academic or vocational, is not likely to become at-risk student. A behavioral problem is a departure from normal(acceptable) behavior beyond a point, to the extent behavioral problems can manifest themselves in many ways. There are interchangeable terms for behavior

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disorders- disruptive behavior disorder, conduct disorders, emotional disorders, and emotional disturbances.

A teacher is a person who provides students direct classroom teaching, or classroom-type teaching in a non-classroom setting. Teachers play an influencing role in development of personality. Listening to child's problems is an important skill of a teacher. The early detection and treatment of children with behavioral problems at an early age may reduce treatment costs and improve quality of life of those children. Teachers are the persons who are caring the school going children for a long time with them in schools when comparing to their parents. So school teachers should have adequate knowledge regarding early identification of behavioral problems of school children which will promote the behavioral status of the children. So the researchers are interested to assess the existing knowledge of school teachers regarding behavioral problems of school children. So in this study we are assessing the

knowledge on behavioral problems of school children among school teachers by providing an informational module regarding behavioral problems of school children.

Objectives

1. To assess the knowledge on behavioral problems of school children among school teachers.
2. To associate the level of knowledge on behavioral problems of school children among school teachers with the selected demographic variables

Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the level of knowledge and the selected demographic variables of school teachers.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Descriptive research design was adopted for this study. The population for the study includes school teachers who are

handling the students in the age group between 6-12 years. The sample selected for the present study was 60 school teachers who fulfilled the inclusion criteria. The study settings were Government High School, CHHATTARPUIR, and MADYA PRDESH. Purposive sampling technique was adopted for the study.

Description of the intervention

Before starting data collection, researcher obtained permission from the Principal in Government Smart Primary School, Chhattarpur, and Madhya Pradesh. Investigator introduced her to the School teacher and developed professional therapeutic relationship with them. The data was collected through the self structured questionnaire is used to assess the knowledge of behavioral problem of school children, among school teachers.

Data analysis

The data was analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistical analysis. The descriptive statistical analysis was done in terms of mean and percentage distribution for the selected demographic variables of school teachers and the inferential statistical analysis was done to associate with the knowledge on behavioral problems of school teachers.

RESULTS

- The knowledge of school teachers on behavioral problems of school children shows that 15 [25%] of school teachers having moderately adequate knowledge and 45[75%] of them have inadequate knowledge and none of the school teachers had adequate knowledge regarding behavioral problems of school children among school teachers. The mean and standard deviation of the study is 14.02 +4.26.
- In association, the level of knowledge among school teachers on behavioral problems with selected demographic variables reveals that none of the demographic variables are non significant with the P value < 0.05.
- The major findings were the age of the school teachers reveals that 29 (48.33%) of the school teachers belongs to the age group of 36 and above and 6 (10%) of them were 31-35 years of age, Sex of the school teachers shows that 7(11.66%) of them were males and 53(88.33%) of them were females, Educational qualification of the school teachers states that 29(48.33%) of the school teachers have completed their under graduation and 31(51.66%) of the school teachers have completed their post-graduation, Marital status of the school teachers states that 48(80%) of them were married and 12(20%) of them were unmarried, Type of family of the school teachers shows that 31(51.66%) of them were nuclear family, 28(46.66%) of them were joint family and 1(1.66%) was in extended family, Type of residence of the school teachers shows that 40(66.66%) of them from urban, 20(33.33%) of them

from rural, Teaching experience of the school teachers reveals that 12(20%) of them have 0-1 year experience, 4(6.66%) of them have 2-3 years of experience, 2(3.33%) of them have 4 years of experience 3-4 years of experience and 42(70%) of them have more than 4 years of experience, The previous knowledge of the school teachers and the table shows that 28(63.33%) of them have previous knowledge and 32(53.33%) of them does not have previous knowledge.

DISCUSSION

This study was conducted to assess the knowledge on behavioral problems of school children among school teachers with a view to develop an informational module in selected schools at puducherry. Descriptive research design was adopted for this study. The population for the study includes school teachers who are handling the students in the age group between 6-12 years. The sample selected for the present study was 60 school teachers who fulfilled the inclusion criteria. The study settings were Government High School, CHHATTARPUIR, and MADYA PRDESH. Purposive sampling technique was adopted for the study. The data was collected through the self structured questionnaire is used to assess the knowledge of behavioral problem of school children, among school teachers.

The first objective of the study is to assess the knowledge on behavioral problems of school children among school teachers. The present study shows that 15 [25%] of school teachers having moderately adequate knowledge and 45[75%] of them have inadequate knowledge and none of the school teachers had adequate knowledge regarding behavioral problems of school children among school teachers. The mean and standard deviation of the study is 14.02 +4.26.

The second objective of the study is to associate the level of knowledge on behavioral problems of school children among school teachers with the selected demographic variables. The association of the level of knowledge among school teachers on behavioral problems with selected demographic variables reveals that none of the demographic variables are non significant with the P value < 0.05.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of the present study shows that not even a single teacher is having an adequate knowledge and majority of them had inadequate knowledge regarding behavioral problems of school children among school teachers. This shows that knowledge of school teachers regarding behavioral problem were poor, so there is a need to improve the knowledge of school teachers about behavioral problem of school children. So health education for school teachers regarding behavioral problems emphasize for the early identification of behavioral problem.

Table 1-Level of knowledge on behavioral problem among school teachers

S. No	Level of knowledge on	Frequency (N=60)	Mean	SD	Percentage
1	Inadequate knowledge	45	11.96	2.46	75%
2	Moderately adequate knowledge	15	20.20	1.66	25%
3	Moderately adequate knowledge	0	0	0	0

Table 2-Association between the of level of knowledge with the selected demographic variables

S. No	Demographic variables		Level of knowledge			x ²	
			Inadequate knowledge	Moderate knowledge	Total	Chi square Test	P Value
1	Age in year	20-25	11	2	13	3.189	3.189
		26-30	10	2	12		
		31-35	3	3	6		
		36 & above	21	8	29		
2	sex	Male	7	8	29	2.642	0.104
		female	38	0	7		
3	Educational Qualification	UG	24	5	29	1.802	0.179
		PG	21	10	31		
4	Marital Status	Married	34	14	48	2.222	0.136
		Unmarried	11	1	12		
5	Type of Family	Nuclear	22	9	31	0.793	0.673
		Joint	22	6	28		
		Extended	1	0	1		
6	Residence	Urban	29	11	40	0.4	0.527
		Rural	16	4	20		
7	Teaching Experience	0-1 Year	10	2	12	1.397	0.706
		2-3 Years	3	1	4		
		4-5 Years	2	0	2		
		More than 4 Years	30	12	42		
8	Previous Knowledge	Yes	19	9	28	1.429	0.232
		No	26	6	32		

REFERENCES

- [1] Bimla Kapoor (RNRN). "Textbook of Psychiatric Nursing", volume 11, Mumbai: Kumar publishing house, 2009.
- [2] Judith M, Schwetz, Sheila. L. Videveck. Lippincott's, "Manual of Psychiatric Nursing care plan", 7th edition, New Delhi: Lippincott's Williams and Wilkins, 2008.
- [3] Wongs. "Essentials of Pediatric Nursing", 7th edition, New Delhi: 2005. Elsevier publications, 2005.
- [4] Piyush Gupta. "Essentials of Pediatrics Nursing", 2nd edition, New Delhi: CBS Publishers and Distributors, 2007.
- [5] Nirai Ahuja. "A short book of psychiatry", 18th edition, New Delhi: Medical Publications, 2013.
- [6] Lalitha. K. "Textbook of Mental Health and Psychiatric Nursing", 8th edition, Bangalore: V. M. G. book house, 2003.
- [7] Suraj. Gupta. Shorthand "Textbook of Pediatrics", 10th edition, New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers Publications, 2004.
- [8] Basavanthappa. "Textbook of Nursing Research", 1st edition, New Delhi: Jaypee publications, 2000.